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Extended abstract: The ConsenCUS Project: Carbon Neutral clusters by Electricity-based Innovations in Capture, Utilisation and Storage

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Abstract

CarbOn Neutral cluSters by Electricity-based iNnovations in Capture, Utilisation and Storage (ConsenCUS) is a 2021-2025 H2020 project. The goals of the project include the development and demonstration of a new, highly efficient CO₂ capture and downstream conversion process. Both processes are aqueous and electricity-based and have a low energy consumption. The projects suggests the location of two carbon capture utilisation and storage (CCUS) clusters in the EU and examines a wide range of environmental, economic and social implications of such clusters.

Keywords: Carbon Capture Demonstration; H2020 EU projects, Carbon Neutral Clusters, CCUS Demonstration Projects

1. Introduction

The EU has set a clear target to curb climate change: a climate neutral industry by 2050. For several crucial EU industries, this means that the CO₂ they emit needs to be captured, utilised and/or stored. The ConsenCUS project (total budget 13.7 MEUR) aims to provide an industrial roadmap to a net-zero carbon future through “Carbon neutral clusters by electricity-based innovations in Capture, Utilisation and Storage” [1]. A wide range of aspects of this concept will be examined by installing a mobile CO₂ capture and utilisation demonstration plant at industrial partners: major cement, magnesia and oil refining sites.

The project presents technological innovations in the three main components of CCUS: (1) carbon capture based on

alkali absorption, coupled to a novel electro dialysis cell (100 kg CO₂/h), (2) conversion of CO₂ to formate and formic acid (5 kg CO₂/h) and (3) safe cyclic loading of CO₂ into salt formations and aquifers for storage.

The capture and conversion routes supplement the conventional thermal, organic-solvent based technologies, as they consume only (renewable) electricity and water, while providing energy and cost-efficiency beyond the current industrial standard (targets: TRL 6-7, 1.4 GJ and €34 per tonne CO₂). Life cycle analysis and techno-economic evaluations will address how the innovations can be exploited, optimising environmental benefits while providing sound business cases for the three sectors participating and beyond.

To contextualize the technological developments, the project will design so-called CO₂ clusters and networks in NW and SE Europe, centred around the demonstration sites. These clusters will be developed in the net-zero framework, which centralises the EU constraint for carbon neutral industry by 2050 [2]. The project partners are spread across the CO₂ value chain and will optimise the CO₂ cluster models based on an interconnected network of emitters fitted with carbon capture and utilisation technology, CO₂ end users and geological storage. Geological modelling will help understand the boundary conditions for back-production of CO₂ after underground storage, which may have a place in the net-zero carbon future, when CO₂ may provide a useful, concentrated source of carbon. In any case, planning joint infrastructure and operation will drive cost down and encourage collaboration.

To examine the societal impact, the project will engage with the communities surrounding the demonstration sites, by clarifying the social and environmental impact of CCUS activities to locals, raising awareness alongside investigating their critical needs. Using a narrative approach, we communicate uncertainties and opportunities to citizens and policymakers [3].

2. Demonstration activities

The ConsenCUS project develops electrochemical innovations for capturing CO₂ and converting it to useful chemicals, potassium formate and formic acid. An important target of the project is to demonstrate the viability of these innovations in real industrial environments. To this end, the project will design and build a mobile demonstration plant (Fig. 1) that will be connected to the flue gas outlets of three major European industrial sites (cement production, oil refinery and magnesite production, with CO₂ levels from 3-20% and varying impurities).

The mobile demonstration plant will capture up to 100 kg/h of the sites' CO₂ and perform various demonstration cycles to establish optimal operation conditions, taking into account different CO₂ concentrations and impurities.

Fig. 1. The ConsenCUS demonstration plant.

CO₂ will be captured from the flue gases using a scrubber tower with alkali solution in water. The spent sorbent will be electrochemically regenerated using a pH swing, while simultaneously separating CO₂, which can be directed towards storage or conversion [4]. The pure CO₂ stream will be electrochemically reduced in a potassium hydroxide solution towards potassium formate and can be further treated electrochemically towards a concentrated formic acid solution, recycling the potassium (Fig. 2) [5]. The end goal for the ConsenCUS technology suite is to go from TRL4 to TRL7, going from lab setups to operating the unit at intermediate scale in actual industrial conditions.

Fig. 2. ConsenCUS flow diagram and demonstration targets of CO₂ capture (left half) and conversion to formate (right). Excess CO₂ may be (temporarily) stored or pumped up at full scale (indicated by the in/out arrows), since renewable electricity and demand have seasonal fluctuations.

3. Net-zero emission framework to define carbon neutral clusters

The ConsenCUS project has the firm ambition to operate the CCUS innovations to allow competitive EU industries with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions. As a part of research efforts, the investment and technology needs for completely net-zero CCUS clusters in North-West and South-East Europe are investigated. Analytically, this is done by imposing a strict net-zero GHG constraint on the involved industry and CCUS activities by 2050. Instead of analysing how well any technology (including those developed in ConsenCUS) performs individually, i.e., how high its GHG emissions are after (partial) mitigation and at what costs, the net-zero-emission framework takes into its optimisation procedures that the whole energy system must be made net-zero, i.e., every residual system emission must be addressed by such measures as CO₂ storage, the introduction of biogenic carbon instead of fossil carbon, direct air capture and/or other greenhouse gas removal (GGR) technologies (Fig. 3, [2]). This innovative framework will be applied to CCUS cluster design and optimisation, LCA, and societal analysis alike.

Fig. 3. Possible configurations of net-zero CO₂ emission systems.

To achieve these targets, collaborating and sharing infrastructure in a network is crucial to cost-competitiveness. This network will be designed bringing together multiple emitters, users and storage locations using a shared transportation infrastructure specific to the industries. This includes specific considerations of the best place for storage buffers, how large those should be, and how to control the amount of energy converted and stored with a system approach in clusters. Time-dependent operation will create an industrial symbiosis with varying availability of electricity and hydrogen, or any similar resource, dependent on weather conditions and seasonal energy flows.

The ConsenCUS project will provide an interface between the project and those living and working within the clusters (Fig. 4 presents an example of a Danish cluster with CO₂ emitters and potential storage sites). Community engagement will be examined by interviews with locals from a range of social groupings, benefits from socio-economic multiplier effects (jobs, environment, economic gain) and how these develop over time.

Fig. 4. CO₂ emitters and potential storage sites onshore Denmark. Data courtesy of the Nordic CCS Competence Centre, <https://data.geus.dk/nordiccs>. Color dots represent CO₂ emissions points, black areas depict the Havnsø and Stenlille structures which are potential storage sites.

4. Summary

The ConsenCUS project is more than a project developing innovative technology. The climate issues which the world is facing need holistic solutions. It is important that the solutions do not sub-optimize single industries, technologies or countries. The ConsenCUS project commits the many different disciplines required to solve such an all-encompassing challenge, both on the specific technical and regional level, but also in a way which can be applied generically.

Technologically, the project develops conceptually different electricity-based capture and conversion innovations that supplement the thermal, organic solvent state-of-the-art CCU solutions, with an especially strong benefit in places where no waste heat is available, or where variable renewable electricity needs to be integrated. A range of different industrial operational environments (including those with hard-to-abate or inherent CO₂ emissions) are part of the ConsenCUS demonstration campaign, providing specific experience with cement, magnesia and refinery flue gases. Cyclic loading of CO₂ into porous rock or aquifers is investigated in the lab and with geological models. To make actual implementation possible, citizens and other stakeholders are engaged to improve our cluster models and infrastructural planning, and to encourage awareness, acceptance or even participation. Together, we plan for a net-zero carbon Europe in 2050.

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